

Assessing Airport Surface Traffic Performance from Open Sources of Aviation Data

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Abstract—This study investigates the potential of crowdsourced open aviation data, specifically ADS-B trajectories and OpenStreetMap infrastructure models, to analyse airport surface operations. Surface position messages in ADS-B often suffer from challenges related to Global Navigation Satellite System localization accuracy and Mode S receiver data reception, such as multipath interference. Similarly, the crowdsourced efforts to enrich OpenStreetMap’s infrastructure data are primarily focused on general mapping purposes rather than detailed operational analysis. In this paper, we review the existing literature on airport surface performance assessment and develop a methodology to adapt these techniques for open ADS-B data. Our approach focuses on filtering trajectory data to map positional information, where available, into a timed sequence of taxiway segments. These sequences are used to calculate key performance indicators from the literature, such as saturation rates, taxi-out time distributions as a function of departing aircraft queue sizes, and flow-density relationships (fundamental diagrams). We apply this methodology to a data set of selected days in 2024 at Zurich International Airport.

Keywords—ADS-B; open data; airport surface traffic; data-based performance evaluation

I. INTRODUCTION

The capacity of an airport is defined as the envelope function describing all possible combinations of maximum number of take-offs n_{DEP} and landings n_{ARR} an aerodrome can handle per unit time under continuous demand [1], [2]. In practice, the capacity of an aerodrome is limited both by *external factors* such as airspace capacity, political and regulatory constraints, or the weather; as well as by *internal, airport-specific factors*. With regard to airport-related factors, the capacity can be affected by operational aspects, such as the runway configuration describing which runways are used for take-offs and/or landings, as well as by the layout of the taxiway and runway system. While capacity bottlenecks caused by operational aspects might be reduced or mitigated by adapting processes, layout-related bottlenecks can often only be addressed by a structural modification of the airport surface network, i.e., the runways, taxiways, and aprons.

Structural adaptations, modifications, or even extensions to the airport surface network cannot be implemented everywhere. Recent airport expansion projects have been relatively limited in North America and Europe, whereas aerodromes in Asia and the Middle East have seen increased development [3]. As demand for air travel is expected to continue to grow [4], airport utilization will increase, particularly at

airports where expansion is not feasible. These aerodromes are exposed to higher levels of congestion, resulting in longer than necessary aircraft taxi times. Consequences include higher pollutant emissions, prolonged noise exposure, and higher internalized and externalized costs for all stakeholders involved [5], [6]. Therefore, it is crucial to objectively measure, analyse, and monitor the efficiency of aircraft surface movements at an airport. This approach allows airport operators to identify bottlenecks and assess their impact on airport capacity. Furthermore, it provides a basis for evaluating the effectiveness of operational and structural measures designed to enhance capacity.

The state-of-the-art offers various metrics to objectively assess the efficiency of airfield operations and provide quantifiable insights into airport utilization. These are based on (i) *counting surface movements*, including departing and arriving aircraft, (ii) *measuring taxi times*, or (iii) conducting detailed studies of *surface traffic flows*.

The simplest metric involves counting taxiing aircraft $N(t)$ at a time t . If $N(t)$ is set in relation to the departure rate $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ or the arrival rate $n_{\text{ARR}}(t)$ of an aerodrome, the *saturation rate* N^* can be determined [7]. The saturation rate is a good indication that an airport is operating at its capacity limit. Efficiency metrics based on the measurement of aircraft taxi times $\tau(i)$ of aircraft i [8]–[10] aim to estimate the so-called *unimpeded taxi times* τ_{unimped} . These represent the taxi times an aircraft would require under ideal conditions, unaffected by external factors such as congestion, weather, or delays. Finally, flow measures deal with the analysis of *surface traffic flows*. For instance, *fundamental diagrams* are used by [11] to characterize the relationship between surface aircraft flow (i.e., aircraft movements per unit time) and surface traffic density (i.e., the number of aircraft per unit length of a given airport surface network element).

Past studies on efficiency measures for airport surface operations focus exclusively on specific airports. Besides, they make use of data sets covering short time periods from a few hours to a few days, which are either proprietary (e.g., traffic data provided by airports [9], [12]; surface radar data provided by airports [11]; ACARS data provided by airlines [13], [14]) or geographically limited (e.g., Airport Surface Detection Equipment–Model X (ASDE-X) data, which only covers 35 major US airports: [8], [15]). To the best of our knowledge, however, the use of open ADS-B trajectory data to evaluate the efficiency of airport surface movements has

not been documented in the literature. In light of this gap, our study investigates whether and how efficiency metrics for airport surface operations can be derived on the basis of open ADS-B trajectory data sourced from the OpenSky Network [16]. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to present and implement generic methods allowing to calculate the following metrics on the basis of ADS-B trajectory data:

- 1) the saturation rate N^* of an airport;
- 2) unimpeded taxi-out times for selected runways; and
- 3) fundamental diagrams for selected elements of airport surface networks.

Our study is illustrated using Zurich International Airport (LSZH), which currently has one of the most comprehensive surface traffic coverage in the OpenSky Network. However, our methods are applicable to any airport with open ADS-B data, making them a valuable resource for future research projects.

The remainder of this study is structured as follows: Section II provides an in-depth overview on airport surface movement efficiency metrics documented in the literature. Section III then introduces methods allowing the determination of selected efficiency measures on the basis of open sources of aviation data. Subsequently, Section IV showcases results obtained when our methods are applied to the example of Zurich International Airport. Finally, the results and limitations of this study are discussed in Section V, while conclusions and outlooks are provided in Section VI.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In the following, we provide an overview of the literature on metrics allowing for an objective evaluation of the efficiency of airfield surface operations. For this purpose, this section is divided into three distinctive parts, which deal with metrics that focus on (i) counting surface movements of taxiing aircraft, (ii) measuring and analysing taxi times, and (iii) conducting in-depth studies of surface traffic flows. Since the departure process is particularly susceptible to congestion, this study will focus exclusively on this aspect.

a) Counting surface movements: Shumsky [12] and Pujet [7] suggested counting the number of departing aircraft $N(t)$ taxiing at time t to make statements about the level of airfield congestion. While this metric is relatively straightforward to measure, it does not indicate whether and where queues of aircraft are formed. As an extension, Pujet [7] proposed to relate $N(t)$ to the departure rate $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ of the airport, where $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ refers to the number of aircraft departing within a certain time interval after time t , e.g., within the hour after t . By observing $N(t)$ and $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ for a large number of times t , the so-called saturation rate N^* , also known as the saturation point, can be determined. For $N(t) \leq N^*$, the departure throughput of the runway $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ increases as a function of $N(t)$. However, as soon as $N(t)$ exceeds the saturation rate N^* , the departure throughput of the runway stagnates or even decreases. In other words, N^* is the point at which the airport is operating at its maximum departure capacity. Consequently, the total number of hours per year an airport operates at $N(t) > N^*$ can be used as a measure of airport congestion.

b) Measuring taxi times: The taxi-out time is another metric commonly recommended in the literature for assessing the efficiency of surface operations at an airport [8]–[10]. The taxi-out time $\tau_{\text{DEP}}(i)$ for a departing aircraft i can be either determined based on data supplied by airports and/or airlines or from aircraft surface trajectory data originating from various sources, such as surface radar or Automatic Dependent Surveillance–Broadcast (ADS-B).

The taxi-out time $\tau_{\text{DEP}}(i)$ of a departing aircraft i is defined as the time interval between leaving the stand and lining-up on the runway for take-off. According to [9], the taxi-out time $\tau_{\text{DEP}}(i)$ consists of the following components

$$\tau_{\text{DEP}}(i) = \tau_{\text{unimped}}(i) + \tau_{\text{TWY}}(i) + \tau_{\text{RWY}}(i), \quad (1)$$

where τ_{unimped} is the so-called *unimpeded taxi-out time*, which is defined as “the estimated taxi-in time for an aircraft by carrier under optimal operating conditions, when congestion, weather, or other delay factors are not significant” [17]. Besides, τ_{TWY} describes the additional taxiing time due to interactions of aircraft i with other aircraft on the apron(s) and taxiways, and τ_{RWY} quantifies the time spent in the departure queue in front of the runway. While τ_{TWY} and τ_{RWY} can be measured based on trajectory data or estimated using appropriate models [9], the determination of the unimpeded taxi-out time τ_{unimped} can be challenging. Indeed, the unimpeded taxi-out time τ_{unimped} is only measurable under *free-flow* conditions, as it describes the time it takes an aircraft to complete the departure process when no external factors such as other traffic, weather, etc. are affecting its departure process. Free-flow conditions exist only if (i) the departure queue $N_Q(i)$, which refers to the number of taxiing aircraft being scheduled to take-off before aircraft i , is exactly one, and (ii) the arrival queue is zero at the same time. Therefore, the entire variability of τ_{unimped} is solely based on internal factors, such as variability due to pilot-controller interactions, main engine start times, push-back, etc. [18].

According to [9], the unimpeded taxi-out time τ_{unimped} for a flight i can be estimated using the following linear regression model

$$\tau(i) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 N_Q(i) + W(i) \quad (2)$$

where β_0 and β_1 are parameters, $W(i)$ is an independent and identically distributed normal random variable with $W_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$, and $N_Q(i)$ is the departure queue for aircraft i . Subsequently, after estimating parameters $\hat{\beta}_0$ and $\hat{\beta}_1$ using the maximum likelihood method, the unimpeded taxi-out time can be determined as:

$$\tau_{\text{unimped}} = \hat{\beta}_0. \quad (3)$$

Unimpeded (average) taxi times can be determined for entire airports as well as for individual elements of the surface network of an aerodrome, e.g., a taxiway section. For this purpose, the average unimpeded taxi-out times of a segment is estimated by averaging the unimpeded taxi-out times of all flights using this segment. Once unimpeded taxi times have been determined, they can be used as baseline figures, allowing the determination of the congestion level of an airport. To this end, one compares observed taxi times of

aircraft at a certain time with the corresponding unimpeded taxi time.

In addition to the unimpeded taxi-out time, the saturation taxi-out time τ^* is another measure that can be used as a baseline to determine the surface efficiency of an airport. According to [9], the saturation taxi-out time τ^* is defined as the average taxi-out time of all flights that have a take-off queue of $N_Q(i) = N^* - 1$. Thus, the saturation taxi-out time represents the time required by aircraft when an airport is operated shortly before the saturation rate N^* is reached. As such, the saturation taxi time can be determined for each segment of the apron and taxiway system of an airport by calculating the average taxi time of all aircraft that have a take-off queue of $N^* - 1$.

c) Studying surface traffic flows: Another approach to evaluate the efficiency of surface movements involves analysing and modelling the underlying traffic flows of arriving and departing aircraft during taxiing operations at an airport. Simaiakis and Balakrishnan [9] proposed to model surface flows at airports using queueing models, while Idris et al. [14] described flows using statistical methods. Ali et al. [19] used Advanced Surface Movement Guidance and Control System (A-SMGCS) data from Singapore Changi Airport to analyse spatio-temporal intersection usage distributions, describing the likelihood of a flight occupying an intersection at a given time after leaving the runway or stand. By evaluating overlaps in these distributions, they quantified the likelihood and severity of taxiing conflicts, enabling the identification of hotspots across all taxiway intersections. Mori [20] adapted the *Nagel-Schreckenberg* (NS) model—a theoretical framework traditionally used to describe traffic flow on highways and roads under the assumption of uniform traffic rules—for application to airports. Using Tokyo Haneda International Airport as a case study, Mori demonstrated that the model could closely replicate observed flow and congestion patterns, particularly under conditions of high traffic volumes. Also building on methods from road traffic analysis, Yang et al. [11] characterized airport surface flows at Guangzhou Baiyun Airport using fundamental diagrams. Originating from road traffic theory, fundamental diagrams describe the relationship between traffic flow (i.e., vehicles per unit of time) and traffic density (i.e., vehicles per unit length of a road segment) for a given road segment [21]. While drivers on roads can independently adjust their speed and select their routes, aircraft surface movements on aerodromes are tightly regulated. Therefore, Yang et al. [11] first validated whether fundamental diagrams could be applied to elements, i.e., links, of airport surface networks, such as taxiway segments and apron areas. Using secondary surveillance radar data from Guangzhou Baiyun Airport, they demonstrated the existence of fundamental diagrams for these elements, which ultimately enabled them to derive the Macroscopic Fundamental Diagram (MFD) for the airport. As such, the MFD captures the relationship between the aerodrome’s departure rate, $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$, represented by the runway throughput (number of flights per 15 minutes), and the taxi-out traffic density, measured by the number of departing aircraft $N(t)$ occupying the taxiways and aprons at a given time t .

III. METHODOLOGY

In the following, we present the methods used in this study. Sections III-A and III-B describe the open sources of aviation data utilized. Then, Section III-C explains the filtering process applied to surface trajectories, while Section III-D details the mapping of trajectory data to known elements of the airport surface network. Finally, in Section III-E, we describe how these methods were applied to Zurich Airport to determine its saturation rate, estimate unimpeded taxi-out times for various runways, and construct the fundamental diagram for a selected taxiway.

A. ADS-B surface trajectory data

The authors operate two ADS-B receivers with line-of-sight on most surface areas of Zurich Airport. Both receivers feed the OpenSky Network [16] databases. Therefore, we downloaded data within the bounding box of the airport, and kept only trajectories for arriving and departing aircraft. Trajectory data of aircraft overflying the airport and surface vehicles is filtered out. To keep the computational requirements of our study within limits, we exclusively downloaded ADS-B data for ten days in the year 2024. As indicated in Table I, these days were chosen to cover a wide variety of operating conditions in terms of weather conditions and runway configurations employed.

TABLE I. Selected days for our data set

Date	Selection criterion
January 9	lowest daily high temperature
January 20	lowest recorded temperature
February 1	regular day
April 1	regular day
May 31	most daily precipitation
July 28	most number of departing aircraft
August 12	highest recorded temperature
August 16	highest daily low temperature
October 1	regular day
November 16	fog conditions

B. Open geodata on airport infrastructure

Official information on the structure of airport infrastructure, e.g., dimension and location of runways, taxiways, stands, etc., are in most countries publicly accessible through national electronic Aeronautical Information Publication (eAIP) platforms, principally in PDF format. In addition, crowdsourced platforms such as *OpenStreetMap* play a significant role in modelling airport infrastructures. As such, *OpenStreetMap* uses structured data representations, employing nodes, ways, and relations associated with metadata information. Specifically, the ‘aeroway’ tag on *OpenStreetMap* encompasses various elements of airport infrastructure. While not all airports are fully modelled, dedicated enthusiasts regularly contribute to refining these models using satellite imagery and eAIP data.

The *cartes* library, which is integrated into the traffic package [22], facilitates the retrieval of *OpenStreetMap* data through the Overpass API. The data is downloaded, then transformed into a *GeoDataFrame*, where the geometry

associated with each element is represented as a Point, LineString, or Polygon. For this study, our focus is particularly on essential airport elements for aircraft trajectories, i.e., runways, taxiways, parking positions, and apron areas, as illustrated in Figure 1 for the example of Zurich Airport.

Figure 1: OpenStreetMap federates many enthusiast contributors who continuously improve the modelling of the structure of airports. This map of Zurich Airport (LSZH) depicts a central part of the airport with buildings (black), runways (blue), taxiways (green), parking positions (orange), and apron areas (light blue).

C. Filtering ADS-B surface trajectories

Aircraft on the ground send a specific type of ADS-B messages called *surface messages* (BDS 0, 6): each frame contains latitude, longitude, ground speed, and track information (instead of altitude information). The type code, a 5-bit integer which is part of all ADS-B messages, encodes some uncertainty information about the aircraft’s position. As for ground speed, its precision varies depending on the aircraft speed value interval, as shown in Table II from [23].

TABLE II. Surface position movement (ground speed)

Encoded speed	Ground speed range	quantization
0	<i>speed not available</i>	
1	<i>stopped</i> ($v < 0.125$ kt)	
2–8	$0.125 \leq v < 1$ kt	0.125 kt steps
9–12	$1 \text{ kt} \leq v < 2$ kt	0.25 kt steps
13–38	$2 \text{ kt} \leq v < 15$ kt	0.5 kt steps
39–93	$15 \text{ kt} \leq v < 70$ kt	1 kt steps
94–108	$70 \text{ kt} \leq v < 100$ kt	2 kt steps
109–123	$100 \text{ kt} \leq v < 175$ kt	5 kt steps
124	$v \geq 175$ kt	
125–127	<i>reserved</i>	

The quality of Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) signals received and processed by aircraft while on the ground, which is subject to various sources of interference and reflections of signals, affects the ADS-B data quality. Even with enough receivers having line-of-sight to all parking positions and taxiways, data points may be missing in various parts of the surface trajectory. We addressed this issue in [24], by introducing surface trajectory filtering by incorporating a

constraint into a Kalman filter to align trajectories with the documented geometries of an airport’s taxiway system.

D. Mapping surface trajectories to airport elements

To carry out statistical analyses of the usage of stands, taxiways, and runways, the observed surface ADS-B trajectories of arriving and departing aircraft must be assigned to the various airport elements in the geodata set. For this purpose, we created a graph representation of the elements of the airport surface network using the *cartes* library. As the whole Overpass API revolves around nodes, ways, and relations, the conversion of ways to graph edges connecting two nodes with *geographic* (i.e., a LineString feature) and *metadata information* (i.e., the type of infrastructure, such as runways, taxiways, parking positions, etc.) is direct.

A limitation of the crowdsourced approach is the difficulty in constructing a clean, well-structured graph that forms a single connected component, due to the following factors:

- duplicated nodes: some nodes have different identifiers, but identical positions;
- unconnected nodes: some nodes geographically appear to create a connection between two taxiways, but the topological connection is absent; and
- little to no effort has been made to topologically connect elements of different categories. Therefore, parking positions often appear unconnected to taxiways, and taxiways unconnected to runways they intersect.

We addressed the limitations of this approach using specific functions in the *traffic* library [22], aiming to achieve a graph representation of the taxiway and runway system of an airport. Therefore, the shortest path between two nodes of the graph (typically a parking position and a runway threshold) can be determined with pathfinding algorithms. For the purpose of our study, we assumed an open data-based graph representation \mathcal{G} of Zurich Airport, irrespective of potential future enhancements to the graph construction method. The mapping of a flight’s surface trajectory to airport elements defined in the graph \mathcal{G} was performed through the following steps, as also illustrated in Figure 2:

- 1) Extract the surface part of the observed trajectory data (see *thick blue lines* in Figure 2): for landing, select the part of trajectory after crossing the runway threshold; for take-offs, select the part of trajectory before the first positive vertical rate value;
- 2) compute intersections of the trajectory with all edges (see *thin blue lines* in Figure 2) of \mathcal{G} : as taxiway elements are mostly modelled as LineString structures, we buffer them by 18 m (8 m for parking positions);
- 3) identify the closest nodes to the first and last positions of the surface aircraft trajectory;
- 4) compute the shortest path (see *orange lines* in Figure 2) between the two nodes, where edges have a zero weight if they intersect the trajectory, and a weight equal to the length in meter of the segment otherwise.
- 5) compute intersections of the trajectory with the shortest path; fill time information of missing edges with linear interpolation.

By applying the described process to an observed surface trajectory, a sequence of taxiway segments, each with corresponding start and end timestamps, is assigned to the flight. In the examples illustrated in Figure 2, the first trajectory is ready to depart (aircraft crews *tend to* switch on their transponder when they are ready) around 10:31Z and is matched to its parking position (including the pushback phase) for about 10 minutes. The second example does not contain any pushback information, and the trip to the runway threshold looks uninterrupted.

E. Airport performance evaluation

On the basis of the identified sequences of taxiway segments used by aircraft covered in the data set mentioned, we estimated the saturation rate N^* , unimpeded taxi-out times τ_{unimped} , as well as the fundamental diagram of a single taxiway segment for Zurich Airport.

Following [10], the *saturation rate* N^* is estimated graphically using a scatter plot of the observed take-off rates $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ versus the number of taxiing aircraft on the ground $N(t)$. To this end, the take-off rate was determined for a time period between $t - \Delta t$ and $t + \Delta t$ (for a Δt of 30 minutes). The take-off rate is the number of aircraft taking off within a time frame of an hour; we count the number of departing aircraft based on the timestamps extracted together with taxiway segments. Then, by determining the median take-off rate for all observed values of $N_Q(i)$, we were able to determine the saturation rate graphically.

The *unimpeded taxi-out times* were estimated for runways 16, 28, and 32, which are the runways most used for departures at Zurich Airport. Making use of the methodology proposed by [9], the unimpeded taxi-out were derived by estimating the unknown coefficients β_0 and β_1 of the linear regression model shown in Equation 2. To fit the linear regression model to our ADS-B surface trajectory-based observations, we used the ordinary least squares method, as provided in the statsmodels library. For each aircraft, in addition to computing taxi-out duration, we count the number of aircraft taking off between the beginning and the end of the taxi phase of the reference aircraft.

Finally, we established the *fundamental diagram* for a single segment of taxiway A, that is parallel, to the south of runway 28, right before reaching the runway threshold. For this purpose, we measured both the duration aircraft spent on this taxiway segment and the number of aircraft being present on the segment per unit time. In a second step, we drew a triangular fundamental diagram on the resulting scatter plot. The convex hull includes all trajectory samples that are not considered as outliers due to difficult corner cases in the data preprocessing.

Figure 2: Trajectories with incomplete coverage, matched to a sequence of taxiways: the first flight starts at the gate/parking position (E58) while the second one only gets data from after the pushback, on November.

IV. RESULTS

In the following, we first present the raw data of our measurements for two selected days at Zurich Airport. Subsequently, we focus on the airport performance evaluation measures described in Section III-E, namely the observed saturation rate N^* , the observed taxi-out times for runways 16, 28, and 32, as well as the fundamental diagram for a segment of taxiway A.

A. Traffic patterns

Zurich Airport operates a variety of runway configurations, referred to as *concepts*, which can change throughout the day. These include the following concepts:

- the *North concept*: landing on runway 14 (or 16), take-off from runways 28 and 16;
- the *East concept*: landing on runway 28, take-off from runway 32 (or 34);
- the *South concept*: landing on runway 34, take-off from runways 32 and 28.

Figure 3 showcases the utilization of taxiways and runways, as well as the average duration of their use, for landing and take-off operations across two days (09. January 2024 and 28. July 2024) with varying runway configurations at Zurich Airport.

Figure 3 uses colours to represent the average time aircraft spend on each airport element and line widths proportional to the number of aircraft using these elements. The upper diagram illustrates taxiing movements on 9 January 2024, where strong easterly winds required departures from runways 10 and 16 as well as landings on runway 14. The parallel dark red segments along taxiways near the de-icing pads northwest and east of the midfield concourse indicate extended dwell times, suggesting de-icing operations.

The lower diagram depicts ground traffic on 28 July 2024, showing that runways 16, 28, and 32 were used for departures. Queues are evident on taxiway A before runway 28 and taxiway E before runway 16, reflecting the need for coordination between take-offs from runway 16 and landings on runway 14, particularly due to the potential for go-arounds. Aircraft using runway 16 for take-offs may interact with aircraft flying a go-around on runway 14. Furthermore, minor slowdowns are indicated by the colours for aircraft taxiing after landing on runway 14 or before taking off from runway 32 when crossing runway 10/28.

B. Airport performance evaluation metrics

Using surface aircraft trajectory data of Zurich Airport for all days specified in Table I, we plotted the observed take-off rate $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ versus the observed number of taxiing aircraft $N(t)$ in Figure 4. The diagram contains a series of box plots specifying the observed take-off rates per unique value of $N(t)$. Furthermore, the orange markers indicate the median take-off rate, provided it is statistically significant (for this reason, no markers are shown for $N(t) > 8$). The saturation rate of $N^* = 8$, as highlighted in Figure 4, was determined based on the definition provided in Section II. As illustrated in the figure, the departure rate $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ starts to stagnate at $N(t)$ values around 7 to 8 movements and even suggests a declining trend for $N(t) > 8$.

Figure 5 summarizes the observed taxi-out times τ_i versus the departure queue $N_Q(i)$ for runways 16, 28, and 32. These runways were selected as representative examples, as these are most frequently used for take-offs in Zurich. The violin plots provide insight into both the data density and the inherent variance resulting from the varying distances between parking positions and each runway threshold. Following Equation 2, we fitted a linear regression to these plots. The

Figure 3: Utilization maps of taxiways and runways at Zurich Airport, encompassing several modes of operation

resulting R^2 values, as well as the estimated coefficients, are summarized in Table III. As such, the estimated unimpeded taxi-out time τ_{unimped} , which corresponds to the value $\hat{\beta}_0$ in Equation 3, is 12 minutes 5 seconds, for runway 16, 6 minutes 15 seconds for runway 28, and 7 minutes 30 seconds for runway 32.

Figure 6 depicts the fundamental diagram generated with surface ADS-B trajectory data for a segment of taxiway A, i.e., between the intersection of taxiway A with taxiway Inner and the threshold of runway 28. The blue scatter points represent the observed measurements for flow (number of aircraft per minute) and density (aircraft per meter of taxiway). To increase readability, the scatter points are jittered

Figure 4: Observed take-off rates $n_{\text{DEP}}(t)$ as a function of the number of taxiing aircraft $N(t)$

TABLE III. Unimpeded taxi-out time (linear regression)

	Runway 16	Runway 28	Runway 34
R^2	0.1993	0.3980	0.3023
$\hat{\beta}_0$	12.0812	6.2411	7.4700
t statistics	26.8214	30.7601	21.3883
p -value	6.84e-83	4.67e-131	4.07e-63
$\hat{\beta}_1$	1.0327	2.1198	2.3419
t statistics	8.7990	21.2509	11.6265
p -value	9.71e-17	2.57e-77	3.35e-26

with a Gaussian noise on the x -axis to give an idea of density. The blue shaded area represents the fundamental diagram identified for the taxiway segment.

V. DISCUSSION

We used Zurich Airport as an example to demonstrate the practical applicability of our methods. In a first step, we collected surface traffic data and plotted the resulting traffic patterns for two selected days in Figure 3. These visualizations result in clear maps that effectively highlight bottlenecks in the airport surface network and illustrate how resulting queues impact taxiing traffic. Such illustrations are highly practical for analysing day-to-day operations. However, rather than analysing an entire day at once as conducted in Figure 3, one could also select specific time intervals where only one runway configuration was in use. This approach would allow the generation of surface traffic patterns for each runway configuration employed at the airport. In a subsequent step, the identified bottlenecks for each configuration could then be examined, and targeted strategies to mitigate or eliminate them could be developed.

We estimated a saturation rate N^* of 8 simultaneously taxiing departing aircraft for Zurich Airport. This value is notably lower than the value of 20 movements reported for Philadelphia Airport in the US [10]. This discrepancy can

Figure 5: Observed taxi-out times distribution

Figure 6: Fundamental graph for the last segment of taxiway A before the threshold of runway A

be attributed to several factors, most notably the significantly larger size of Philadelphia Airport compared to Zurich. At this point, we emphasize that the identified saturation rate is only an estimate. As can be seen from Figure 4, the number of samples for $N_Q(i) \geq 7$ becomes increasingly limited, making

an exact determination of the saturation rate impossible. There are two primary reasons for this lack of data. First, our analysis includes only ten days in 2024, restricting the available data points. Second, Zurich Airport, like many other European airports, makes use of *departure metering*, where departing aircraft are held at the gate until sufficient runway capacity is available. In contrast, this practice is less common at many North American airports [25], [26].

Using a linear regression model as specified in [9], we estimated the unimpeded taxi-out times for runways 16, 28, and 32 at Zurich Airport. The results in Table III show that these unimpeded taxi-out times range from 6 minutes 15 seconds to 12 minutes 5 seconds, with the shortest time observed for runway 28 and the longest for runway 16. This aligns with operational conditions, as runway 28 has the shortest average taxiing distances, while runway 16 has the longest. The unimpeded taxi-out times τ_{unimped} , corresponding to $\hat{\beta}_0$, are associated with extremely low p -values in all three cases, indicating their significant influence on the response variable and their importance in the linear regression models. However, the Pearson correlation coefficients R^2 are relatively low for all three models, reflecting the high variability in the data, as evident in Figure 5. In particular, runway 16 exhibits the lowest R^2 value of 0.1993, which suggests that the relationship between the taxi-out time $\tau(i)$ and the departure queue $N_Q(i)$ is not well-captured by a linear model. This may be due to the dependency of departures from runway 16 on arrivals on runway 14, as explained in Section IV-A.

Figure 6 illustrates the relationship between traffic flow and traffic density for the segment of taxiway A just before the threshold of runway 28. Following the approach outlined in [11], we chose a triangular fundamental diagram to represent this relationship. In the diagram, the ascending line represents the *free-flow branch*, the descending line corresponds to the *congestion branch*, and the point where the two lines intersect, at approximately 0.0011 aircraft per meter of taxiway, marks the *critical density*. In the free-flow branch, aircraft taxi at relatively high speeds with minimal interference from other traffic. Conversely, in the congestion branch, aircraft taxiing speeds are significantly reduced due to interactions with other aircraft, leading to the formation of queues. Besides, the limited number of days considered in our study and the use of departure metering at Zurich Airport result in sparse data for *high* densities, which is evident from the few scatter points on the right-hand side of Figure 6. Additionally, it becomes evident that there are no observations for *low* flow and *high* density conditions. This is a common phenomenon in fundamental diagrams: as traffic density increases, the likelihood of queuing rises. While the average taxiing speed of aircraft decreases due to increased interactions, the minimum observed traffic flow still rises with density because the higher number of aircraft compensates for the reduced speed. Indeed, extremely low traffic flow values at high densities are rare and typically occur only during complete traffic breakdowns, such as when a runway is closed due to an incident.

This study has certain limitations in both the methods used and the results presented. Most notably, we analysed ADS-B data for Zurich Airport from only ten selected days

in 2024 to reduce computational and processing effort. This limited scope means that the airport performance metrics presented in Section IV are intended to be exemplary rather than comprehensive. Gathering more reliable metrics would require an extended observation period, spanning several months or even a full year. Such an analysis is technically feasible given the availability of open-access ADS-B data from the OpenSky Network [16].

A further limitation lies in the completeness of the ADS-B trajectories used. Ground-based ADS-B receivers require a clear line-of-sight to accurately receive and decode ADS-B messages transmitted by aircraft. While this condition is typically easier to achieve for airborne aircraft, it poses greater challenges for those on the ground. As a result, the methods outlined in this study for evaluating airport operational efficiency are suitable only for airports with adequate ground coverage, ensuring direct line-of-sight to aprons, taxiways, and runways. This is the reason why Zurich Airport has been chosen as the focus of this study due to its excellent ground coverage within the OpenSky Network.

ADS-B data may still contain errors and gaps, even at aerodromes with excellent coverage. Errors may stem from multi-path effects in the GNSS data, which aircraft use to determine their position before broadcasting it via ADS-B messages. Conversely, gaps may arise when pilots do not switch on the transponder on the stand and only do so later during taxiing. In order to improve data quality, it is therefore essential to use appropriate filtering algorithms. In our study, we tried to reconstruct the most plausible path of a taxiing aircraft. Other filtering approaches can be based on the variant of the Kalman filter we presented in [24], which tries to match the observed surface trajectories with the elements of the airport surface network. However, regardless of the filter used, the surface trajectories may still contain errors due to certain corner cases even after filtering. Although these corner cases do not have a major impact on the data quality from a statistical point of view, they can be analysed in more detail in further work in order to improve the existing filtering methods for surface trajectories.

VI. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOKS

In this study, we presented methods for estimating the saturation rate N^* of an airport, unimpeded taxi-out times τ_{unimped} , and fundamental diagrams for selected taxiways using open sources of aviation data. To apply these methods to Zurich Airport, which was chosen as an example, we first generated usage statistics for all airport surface network elements, including runways, taxiways, and aprons. These statistics were derived by filtering surface trajectories and mapping them to the corresponding airport network elements. Finally, we adapted existing methodologies from the literature to enable the estimation of the aforementioned performance metrics based on the collected usage statistics.

Our results indicate that open-access ADS-B surface trajectories can be effectively used to assess the performance of an airport's ground operations. Specifically, for Zurich Airport, we determined a saturation rate of $N^* = 8$ taxiing movements and unimpeded taxi-out times τ_{unimped} ranging

from approximately 6 minutes for runway 28 to 12 minutes for runway 16. Additionally, we derived the fundamental diagram for a section of taxiway A. Since our analysis was based on trajectory data from only ten selected days to reduce computational demands, the results should be viewed as being illustrative rather than comprehensive. This limitation could easily be addressed by extending the observation period to several months or even years.

Our study has demonstrated that open sources of aviation data can effectively assess and evaluate airport surface performance, provided that the airport has sufficient receiver coverage. The methods introduced in this study are practical tools for airports to perform detailed analyses with relatively simple means. They enable the identification of bottlenecks in the airport surface network across various runway configurations, as well as the objective evaluation and benchmarking of ground operation efficiency. Several extensions to our research are possible: in addition to determining the airport performance metrics presented in this paper for longer observation periods, so that the results are more meaningful in practice, live monitoring could also be implemented. Such a system would allow live benchmarking of surface operations and thus provide valuable inputs for all stakeholders involved in the Airport Collaborative Decision Management (A-CDM) process.

REPRODUCIBILITY STATEMENT

The implementation details, and the code to reproduce the figures, are publicly available from a GitHub repository: https://github.com/xoolive/airport_queues.

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